

Principal's Transformational Leadership in Education Era 4.0: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: This article aims to find out how the principal's transformational leadership style improves teacher performance in the 4.0 education era. This study uses a literature review method by examining national and international journal articles on Google Scholar. The results of the literature review show that the principal's leadership style has a significant influence on teacher performance. The influence of the principal's transformational leadership in improving teacher performance in the 4.0 education era can be indicated from the following indicators: 1) principals foster self-confidence, motivation and high expectations to achieve a vision of the future together, 2) principals set an example in school attendance, 3) principals become inspiration for school members in improving competence, self-development, and performance, 4) principals become leaders who provide knowledge and ways of thinking in finding information technology-based learning development strategies.

KEYWORDS: Education era 4.0, Principal's leadership, transformational leadership style.

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is an effort or activity to form intelligent human beings in various aspects, both intellectual, social, emotional, and spiritual, skilled and personable and can behave with noble character. Schools as formal education institutions are responsible for producing quality human resources (Rahayu, et al. 2019).

The quality of education can be measured by its position in educating the nation's life and advancing national culture. Teachers are human resources who play a very important role in the teaching and learning process, because without teachers it will be difficult for us to understand the importance of education (Normanianti et al. 2019). The same thing was said Hartono et al (2019) which states that the success of education is determined by the teacher as the main actor in the success of learning in schools. The success of learning in the classroom depends on the ability of a teacher to make creative, varied and innovative planning, implementation of learning and assessment.

This is in line with the meaning of education which starts from teachers and other educators. To optimize it all, a teacher must understand the teacher's performance in carrying out his duties and work (Suhaimi & Rinawati, 2018). The same opinion was expressed by Juhdi (2016), which states that the teacher's role in educational development includes inculcating values, character building, learning centers, providing assistance and encouragement, supervising and fostering, disciplining children, and being role models.

According to Andriani (2019), the main factor that greatly influences teacher performance is the leadership of the principal. In relation to efforts to improve teacher performance, a professional school principal will pay attention to several things that Sallies put forward, namely: 1) having a strong vision or great visibility about the unification of the existing quality of institutions, teachers, and students; 2) have a clear commitment to improve the quality of teachers; 3) provide information related to the quality of education; 4) ensure the needs of students as a concern for institutional activities and policies 5) support the development of education personnel; 6) do not blame the other party if there is a problem without strong evidence; 7) make changes that are good for the institution; 8) build effective teamwork; 9) improve appropriate mechanisms for monitoring and evaluation.

The competencies needed in the 4.0 education era are critical thinking and problem solving skills. This competency is very important for students to have in 21st century learning. Teachers in the 4.0 education era must be able to mix learning so that they can explore these competencies from students. Information and communication technology-based learning models must be applied by teachers in order to build communication, collaboration, critical thinking, and creative competencies (Indrawan et al. 2020).

In relation to the educational mission, Asbari (2020) states that leadership can be interpreted as an effort by the principal to influence, encourage, guide, direct, and move school staff so that they can work effectively in order to achieve the educational and teaching goals that have been set.

Ruslan (2020), school principals have a critical role in ensuring the education process in schools goes well. Thus, ensuring that teachers have carried out their duties properly is part of the principal's responsibility.

Principals as leaders of educational institutions must be able to facilitate and encourage teacher performance improvement along with the development of science and technology. Leadership is an effort made by a person with all his abilities to influence, encourage, guide, direct, and move others to want to work with enthusiasm and full of confidence in achieving common goals (Tanjung et al. 2020).

2. LITERATUR REVIEW

2.1 Principal's Leadership

According to Wahidin (2020), the changes of leaders will change followers' senses, increase moral expectations and inspire them to do everything they can to reach organisational objectives, not because they are forced, but because they want to. According to Bass & Avolio, there are three attributes of transformational leaders. First, awareness of the importance of processes and efforts is increased. Secondly, supports allow Community interests to take precedence over individual interests. Third, the follower must move beyond the material towards a higher level of self-esteem and improvement.

The leadership is a process that must to exist and need to be held in human life as a social creature. The human beings cannot live as society as the nature if they escape themselves from their dependence to other. Life as a community is requires the leader and leadership, the leadership is can to determine the direction or purpose that's desire, and in what the way that direction or aims it can be achieved. In the level of educational institutions such as the schools, the educational leadership can be seen in the micro level of institutions, namely is the headmaster. The headmaster leadership is a leader in the organizational level of the school that will determine how the organization performance with overall (Suharsaputra, 2013).

The leadership's includes the attention to common goals. The leaders is direct their energies to the individuals who are trying to achieve something together. The attention to common goals is gave the leadership an ethical additional tone, because it emphasizes the need for leaders to work with the followers to achieve a specific goal (Northouse, 2013: 6). The emphasis of mutuality is reduces the possibilities that the leaders take an action to followers with the unethical or forced ways. This is increases the possibility that leader and follower will be work together for the common good. The headmaster is a person who is appointed to be a formal leader within an organization in this case is school, a headmaster who has duties and responsibilities to superiors, staffs, and work environment, and performs his duties as educator, administrator and creator of climate's work in order to achieve a goals which has been set (Ahmad, 2013).

Kristiawan et al. (2017) the headmaster is a key into shaping the school culture, where the headmasters should be able to form a positive culture, where his staff share the insight and have a dedication to the school improvement and teaching.

The leadership makes a organization is can move and directed in an effort to achieve the goals that have been set. The leadership is needed to bring the constructive changes in the teaching programs that according to the values and goals of decision makers (Efendi, 2015). The spearhead of education is the learning, and the school buildings its can be simple, as well as the office facilities, transportation equipment, benches, tables and so forth. But the learning is must to receive the greater attention than the other aspect. The quality of education will be at stake through the learning process. Principals have an important role one of them in fostering administrative personnel by giving attention, guidance and training in order to improve the insight of the administrative staff. Based on the description of the data, there are several components of the Principal Leadership Role in fostering social competence (excellent service) School Administration Staff and principal's leadership related to how the guidance strategy conducted by the principal to the administrative staff in carrying out the task (Kristiawan, 2017).

2.2 Transformational Leadership

Bass & Avolio (2000) define transformational leadership theory, based on earlier transformational leadership theory from (Burn,1978). Proponents of transformational leadership believe that transformative leaders create trust, loyalty, admiration and respect among followers, and among followers and leaders, so that they are willing to volunteer to achieve the goals, objectives and vision of the organization.

The four dimensions of transformational leadership through the 4i concept, namely: (1) idealized influence, is behavior that results in respect and confidence; (2) inspiration motivation, is behavior that is able to inspire and motivate others; (3) intellectual stimulation, is a leader who is able to come up with new ideas and provide solutions; (4) individualized consideration, namely the act of listening and attention to the people they lead (Bass & Avolio, 1990).

Robbins (2001) confirms that transformational leaders are those who are able to inspire their followers to change their lives and aspire to a greater purpose and vision. In this definition (Luthans, 2005), transformative leaders are able to change the awareness of their followers, increase their enthusiasm, and motivate them to do their best to achieve organizational goals, not because they are forced to, but they are willing. According to (Bass & Avolio, 2000), there are three characteristics of transformative leaders, namely: first, to increase followers' awareness of the importance of processes and efforts. Second, to motivate followers to prioritize group interests over individual interests. Third, to shift the follower's needs beyond material things to a higher level such as self-esteem and actualization.

Leithwood and Jantzi (2000) identified six main characteristics of transformational educational leaders, namely building a university's vision and goals, providing intellectual stimulation, offering individualized support, symbolizing professional practices and values, showing high performance expectations, and developing structures to foster participation in university decisions. Contingent reward, a subfactor of transactional leadership, relates to situations in which a leader rewards followers for completing an agreed upon task.

2.3 Education Era 4.0

Lubis (2019) stated that the development of industry 4.0 is a big challenge for education World. teacher function not only transfer of knowledge but has an important role in education and learning in schools. Teachers in the 4.0 Education era must be able to improve their skills so that produce graduates who are ready facing industry 4.0. By having the skills to use information and communication technology to support learning, the teacher's role is as a facilitator, inspiration, motivator, imagination, creativity, social empathy, and team work as well as developer of character values cannot be replaced by technology.

According to Wahidin et al (2020) The industrial revolution 4.0 requires students to always think and act creatively and innovatively. This action needs to be taken so that students are able to compete and create jobs based on industry 4.0. This condition is necessary considering that there have been many victims of the industrial revolution 4.0. For example, many professions are being replaced by robotic digital machines, information and communication technology literacy. Various kinds of leadership styles of school leaders have their advantages and disadvantages, but what must be considered is that the application of the leadership style of leaders must be adapted to the conditions that occur in educational institutions today. Every school leader is expected to have an ideal leadership style according to the conditions and demands of the times. The problem is, not all school leaders have the ability to adapt to the demands of change, coupled with the lack of knowledge of school leaders about the transformation of school leadership in the 21st century.

Social media seems to be a powerful communication medium used by students and teachers. Social media is one of the learning media that can be used in the 4.0 education era. The presence of digital classroom social media can be utilized by teachers, so that learning takes place without time and space constraints (Kardiyono et al 2020).

3. METHOD

This literature study by reviewing journals about transformational leadership of school principals. The author conducts this literature study after determining the topic of writing and determining the formulation of the problem. The reviews process was carried out using Google Scholar to search for national and international journals using the keywords "Transformational Leadership of Principals in The Era of Education 4.0". The journal screening time span is limited to the last 5 years, namely 2018 to 2022. Based on the screening, 17.600 journals and articles were identified. After that, they were re-elected according to the research focus that was relevant to the formulation of the problem under study.

Figure 1. Literature review flow

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Result

After searching and sorting journals, the writer then analyzes several journals that are most relevant to the chosen research theme. The journals studied are the results of scientific research using quantitative, qualitative, or mixed methods that have been published in reputable national and international journals.

Table 1: Principal transformational leadership in improving teacher performance in the 4.0 education era

No	Title	Author and Year	Country	Method	Result
1	Develop Leadership Style Model for Indonesian Teachers Performance in Education 4.0 Era	Kadiyono et al. (2020)	Indonesia	Quantitative	The result of this study are transformational leadership style has a positive and significant effect on teacher’s performance.
2	School Principals’ Transformational Leadership Styles and Their Effects on Teachers’ Self-Efficacy.	Christopher DC. Francisco. (2019)	Filipina	Quantitative	All eleven variables of the transformational leadership styles of school principals affect teachers' self-efficacy to a different extent as shown by the non-zero coefficients.
3	Principals' transformational Leadership And Teachers'work Motivation: Evidence From Elementary Schools In Taiwan.	Lee, Y. D., & Kuo, C. T. (2019)	Taiwan	Quantitative	Transformational leadership of elementary school principals and motivation of teachers showed a significantly positive correlation; dimensions of transformational leadership of elementary school principals had predictive power for the overall work motivation of teachers. In particular, the higher the intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration were, the better the work motivation of teachers was.
4	Impact of Transformational Leadership Styles of Principals on Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers	Ahmad, M. (2018).	Pakistan	Qualitative	The samples showed a positive and significant relationship between transformational leadership styles of principals and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

5	Principal transformational leadership and teachers' motivation	Abdullah, A. G. K., Ling, Y. L., & Sufi, S. B. (2018).	Malaysia	Quantitative	There was a significant positive correlation between transformational leadership and teachers' work motivation. Regression analysis also displayed that the best predictor of teachers' motivation is the individual support in transformational leadership
6	Effect of Transformational Leadership Skills on Teachers' Performance at Secondary School Level in Punjab	Ahmad, M. S., Bakhsh, K., & Rasool, S. (2019)	India	Qualitative	Transformational leadership skills have a significant effect on the teacher performance. It was concluded that idealized influence and inspirational motivation are the dominant predictors of the teacher performance.
7	Role of transformational leadership in education 4.0.	Prestiadi, D., Gunawan, I., & Sumarsono (2020,	Indonesia	Literature review	role of transformational leadership in having a strategic position in facing the era of education 4.0. Transformational leadership is done through building commitment and awareness among all stakeholders of educational institutions to actualize themselves and use technological advances, information and communication in the education process.
8	Transformational Leadership and Teacher Empowerment in Education Transformation 4.0	Sihotang, H., (2020)	Indonesia	Quantitative	transformational leadership in educational transformation 4.0 requires that principals have competencies including: (1) having an ideal influence can foster trust and respect from members, (2) have the ability to change the expectations of members by increasing trust in the ability to use technology to solve problems, (3) stimulate members to be more innovative, creative, (4) consider the needs of members to develop themselves.
9	Principal's Leadership in Facing the Revolutionary Era Industry 4.0: The Sociological Perspective of Education	Nursyifa, A., (2019)	Indonesia	Qualitative	The leadership style of the school headmaster that was a democratic transformation following the change, the various knowledge and skills of the headmaster in the era of Revolution 4.0 industry need to be strengthened especially in the skills Technology and entrepreneurship competence.
10	Principal's Leadership Strategy in Facing the Digital Era 4.0	Wening. M.H, & Santosa, A.B., (2020)	Indonesia	Qualitative	The principal's strategy is to improve the quality of human resources in the field of ICT in terms of facilities and infrastructure, openness with developments to deal with things that will happen in the digital 4.0

					era, reactions that will be carried out quickly about changes in the 4.0 era, oriented on the process and results, Mastering the 4C formula, namely: critical thinking, creativity, communication, collaboration.
11	Principal's Leadership in Facing the Revolutionary Era Industry 4.0 : Educational Management Perspective	Jannah, L.K., (2020)	Indonesia	Qualitative	The headmaster leadership style transforms to be democratic as the result of the changing. Also, in the industrial revolution 4.0 eras; the headmaster knowledge and skills need to be strengthened, especially in the technology and entrepreneurship skills.
12	Develop Model of Transactional, Transformational, Democratic and Authocratic Leadership Style for Indonesian School Performance in Education 4.0 Era	Indrawan, I., et al. 2020	Indonesia	Quantitative	Transactional, transformational leadership, democratic leadership style and autocratic leadership style has a positive and significant effect on teacher's performance. This study provides a novelty model for primary school teacher leadership in the education 4.0 era and can be a reference for further research and can also be developed at other school levels and elsewhere.
13	Effect of Leadership Style Toward Indonesian Education Performance in Education 4.0 Era: A Schematic Literature Review	Suyudi et al. (2020)	Indonesia	Systematic literature review	The results of the systematic literature review show that the leadership models of the 6 articles show similar similarities, namely transactional, transformational, charismatic, bureaucratic, and democratic leadership that have a positive and significant effect on the performance of educational institutions.
14	The Influence of Transformational Leadership, Job Satisfaction and Organizational Citizenship Behavior on The Performance of Islamic School Teachers	Tanjung, B.N., et al (2020)	Indonesia	Quantitative	Transformational leadership, job satisfaction and organizational Citizenship behavior have a positive and significant effect on the teacher performance. This new research proposed a model for building the teacher performance among the Islamic school teachers in Jakarta through transformational leadership, job satisfaction and organizational citizenship.
15	Did Transformational, Transactional Leadership Style and Organizational Learning Influence Innovation Capabilities of School Teachers during Covid-19 Pandemic?	Supriadi, Oding. et al (2020)	Indonesia	Quantitative	Transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on the innovation capabilities of teachers. Novelty of this new research proposes a model for building innovation capabilities among teachers through transformational and transactional leadership and organizational learning.

4.2 Discussion

Based on literature studies from several international journals, there is an influence of the principal's transformational leadership style on teacher performance, Kadiyono et al (2020). The principal needs to pay attention to the leadership style he uses in encouraging and directing teachers so that they can improve their performance well. The principal's leadership style and communication pattern have a significant effect on the work motivation of teachers in schools (Lee et al, 2019).

Indrawan et al (2020) concluded that transformational management has a good and important impact on the success of teachers. The results of the same study were stated by Tanjung et al (2020) that the transformations leader has positive and important effects on teacher performance. Ahmad (2018), also emphasized that the principal's transformational leadership style has a significant effect on teacher job satisfaction in schools.

Based on the findings for the hypothesis test, Supriyadi et al. (2020) stated principal leadership have a strong and essential influence on the capacity of teachers to innovate. Christopher (2020) also concluded there the positive and important impact of transformational leadership on teachers self efficacy.

The principal's leadership strategy in dealing with the digital era 4.0 based on the results of research by Wening (2020), namely: 1) Improving the quality of human resources in the field of information technology and computers in terms of facilities and the infrastructure; 2) Openness with development to deal with things will occurred in the era of 4.0; 3) The reaction that will be done quickly about changes in era 4.0; 4) Oriented to process and results; 5) Mastering the 4C formula, namely: critical thinking, creativity, communication, collaboration.

Education in the industrial revolution 4.0 was marked by a change in the way of learning from the conventional one using old methods to modern education in new ways. Education in the industrial revolution 4.0 is no longer merely a learning process that is limited by classrooms or time, education in the industrial revolution 4.0 demands for the widest possible openness of access to the use of communication and information technology through digital and cyber-based learning systems. The presence of the classes on line, that learning is not limited to the meeting in the classroom, but the learning process can be carried over long distances with classes on line, online books, online presence and more activity-based learning online. Learning in the 4.0 era was oriented towards digital lifestyles, thinking tools, learning research and the workings of knowledge. Learning orientation in the industrial revolution 4.0 is a way of working knowledge, strengthening thinking tools, and digital lifestyle. The way knowledge works is the ability to collaborate in teams with different locations and with different tools, strengthening thinking tools is the ability to use technology, digital tools, and services, and digital lifestyles are the use and adjustments to be able to use digital products (Prestiadi et al. 2020)

5. CONCLUSION

The author concludes that the principal's transformational leadership style has a positive effect on teacher performance in schools. This means that the principal's transformational leadership style plays an important role in encouraging, directing, and motivating teachers in improving their performance in realizing quality learning with a digital approach.

In the era of education 4.0, school principals must be able to facilitate the availability of information technology equipment and computers. Teacher competence must also continue to be improved in order to be able to keep up with the development of science and technology that is moving so fast. For this reason, school principals as leaders of educational institutions need to have a quick response in dealing with changes in the social order in society by fostering critical, creative, communicative, and collaborative thinking skills.

This study recommends that principals should be competent in applying transformational leadership to improve teachers' performance and innovation in accordance with the school suitability and the needs of the situation.

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